

Effect of Impact Damage on Compression Fatigue Response of AS4/PEEK Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT: In this paper some of experimental observations obtained by post-impact compression fatigue tests are reported. Specimens used in the present study were made from AS4/PEEK prepregs. The layup was $[+45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$. The impact load caused multiple interlaminar delaminations that were geometrically distributed like a frustum of a cone in through-the-thickness direction. The damage patterns observed in the post-impact compression fatigue tests, e.g. fiber microbuckling and kinking in the 0-degree layer, were quite similar to those in open-hole laminates and impacted laminates under uniaxial compression. However, amounts of impact damage affected compression fatigue behavior. In the case of the specimens with large impact damage, the rear side delamination grew widthwise during compression fatigue. On the other hand, in the case of the specimens with small impact damage, lateral cracks emanated from the edge of the impact crater during fatigue.

KEYWORDS: AS4/PEEK composite, Impact, Compression, Fatigue, Damage

INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials to aircraft primary structures is increasing due to their light weight and high strength nature. However, the excellent mechanical properties of the composite materials can be significantly reduced by a low velocity impact, such as dropped tools during maintenance and runway stones during taxing. A compression-after-impact (CAI) strength of composite structures, in particular, is seriously reduced, even if impact damage is not detectable by visual inspection. A number of investigations [1,2,3,4] etc. have been conducted to estimate the sensitivity of the CAI strength to low velocity impact damage. Fatigue behavior of impacted composite laminates has been studied extensively over the past decade as well. Swanson et al. [5] conducted compression fatigue tests of open hole specimens and impact-damaged specimens to compare the fatigue resistance of a toughened resin system with a conventional brittle resin system. Ding et al. [6] investigated tension-tension and tension-compression fatigue behavior of impact-damaged specimens. Beheshty et al. [7] studied the validity of a proposed fatigue-life model for predicting the lives of impact-damaged laminates by comparing experimental results of tension-tension, tension-compression and compression-compression fatigue tests with their life-prediction model. Mitrovic et al. [8] investigated to determine the influence of loading parameters on tension-compression and compression-compression fatigue behavior of impact-damaged laminates. However, damage growth mechanisms on post-impact fatigue response have not been fully understood and an efficient damage-tolerance methodology of post-impact composite laminates has not been established. The objective of this study is to investigate mechanisms of compression fatigue behavior of impacted composite laminates. In this paper some of experimental observations obtained by post-impact compression fatigue tests are reported.

EXPERIMENTS

Specimens

Quasi-isotropic laminates made from an AS4/PEEK material system were used in this study. The layup sequence of $[+45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$ was selected because it is most commonly used in CAI tests [1]. The AS4/PEEK prepreg APC-2 was laid up by hand and hot-pressed, following the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. After manufacture, each panel, 300 mm by 300 mm in size, was inspected using an ultrasonic C-scan system Canon M-500A to ensure good quality. The panels had a nominal

thickness of 4 mm. Each panel was cut to dimensions of 135 mm long by 35 mm or 50 mm wide using a diamond-tipped slitting wheel. The 35 mm wide specimens were used for evaluating the fatigue behavior of the undamaged laminate, while the 50 mm wide specimens were used for impact and post-impact fatigue tests.

Impact Test

Impact tests were performed using a drop-weight test rig with a 2.2 kg impactor having a 12 mm diameter hemispherical tip. The specimens were clamped between two picture frames with 35 mm diameter window and the impactor was captured on the rebound after impact to prevent secondary strikes. The impactor velocity was measured using a laser displacement sensor. The impact energy was defined as the kinetic energy of the impactor just at the moment of first contact with the specimen. The impact energy is normalized by dividing by the thickness of the specimen. The normalized impact energy level was 0.5 to 1.7 J/mm in this study, which is rather low in comparison with other CAI researches [1] etc. The damage area induced by the impact load was measured by using the ultrasonic C-scan system.

Fig. 1. Compression test fixture.

Static and Fatigue Test

Static compression tests and compression fatigue tests were conducted in a 100 kN servo-hydraulic Instron 8501 testing machine with an end-loading fixture as shown in Fig. 1, which was built after that developed by Shimokawa et al. [9]. Specimens were placed in the fixture without tabs and were tightly clamped with binding grips. This fixture does not have an anti-buckling device of the kind prescribed by ASTM D 695, but prevents an out-of-plane direction moving of the specimen by a pair of supporting guides for the whole of the fixture. The compression load is given from end-sections of the specimen with the binding grips. A gage length of 35 mm for the compression specimen was chosen to prevent global buckling.

The compression-compression fatigue tests were carried out at 1 Hz with constant-amplitude sinusoidal loading, under ambient laboratory conditions. The maximum compressive stress of the cyclic loading was chosen to be 70% to 98% to the ultimate compressive strength. Low cycle fatigue tests were conducted in order to investigate damage growth mechanisms in post-impact compression

fatigue. The minimum compressive stress during fatigue was fixed to -2.5 MPa.

In some cases monitoring damage progression during fatigue was done periodically using the ultrasonic inspection to assess the change of the damaged area as a function of the number of fatigue cycles. Some tests were interrupted prior to catastrophic failure, in order to provide specimens with significant damage for sectioning studies.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact-induced damage was mainly delaminations. The delamination area increased away from the impacted front face towards the back face and 3-dimensional distribution of the multiple delaminations created geometrically a frustum-of-cone shape in through-the-thickness direction as illustrated in Fig. 2. Ishikawa et al. [1] introduced an effective diameter D_e for unified description of CAI strength behavior obtained by various CAI test methods. The effective diameter D_e is defined as the diameter of a hypothetical cylinder with equivalent area to the delamination geometry as shown in Fig. 2. We also adopt the parameter D_e to describe the size of the impact-induced delaminations. In the case of our laminates, a brim portion near the back face in the delamination geometry, which is mentioned by Ishikawa et al. [1], could not be found. This disappearance of the brim portion may be related to that our material system AS4/PEEK is one of tougher composites as pointed out by them.

Fig. 2. Schematic of impact-induced delaminations.

Figure 3 shows relationships between the effective diameter of delaminations D_e and the normalized impact energy. Impacted specimens displayed a large scatter in the delamination diameter. This scatter may be attributed to the inconsistency in the experimental setup, or that the impact energy levels were near the threshold level to cause damage in the specimen as pointed out by Davies et al. [3].

Figure 4 shows relationships between a permanent dent of the impacted point and the normalized impact energy. The permanent dent induced by the impact loading indicates little scatter in comparison with the delamination diameter shown in Fig. 3. The less scatter trend of the permanent dent may be due to that the permanent dent is caused by accumulation of internal damage in the impacted laminate.

Figure 5 shows relationships between the permanent dent and the effective diameter of delaminations. The permanent dent increased with the size of the effective delamination diameter. The increasing rate of the permanent dent in Fig. 5 was however gradually dropped.

Fig. 3. Relationships between effective delamination diameter and normalized impact energy.

Fig. 4. Relationships between permanent dent of impacted point and normalized impact energy.

Fig. 5. Relationships between permanent dent of impacted point and effective delamination diameter.

Fig. 8. Relationships between normalized residual stiffness and normalized number of cycles.

A specimen with a relatively large impact-induced delamination (D_e/b of 0.33) was inspected using the pulse echo system to assess damage progression during fatigue. The specimen was cyclically subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 327 MPa. Figure 9 shows C-scan images of this specimen. Figure 9(a) indicates the impact-induced delaminations and (b) represents a delamination growth during the post-impact fatigue test. The loading direction is up and down in Fig. 9. Examination of the C-scan images in Fig. 9 reveals that the impact-induced damage grew widthwise on the rear side of the specimen up to the 500th cyclic loading. A C-scan image just after the 1,000th loading showed the delamination on the rear side extended rightward in 2 mm more.

Fig. 9. Damage growth of an impacted specimen with a ratio D_e/b of 0.33 as observed by ultrasonic C-scan images. (Fatigue life of this specimen was 1,606.)

Figure 10 shows photographs of an unimpacted specimen in fatigue. The specimen was cyclically subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 507 MPa. The number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 638. Figure 10(a) represents the specimen at two cycles before the fracture. We could not see any failure in Fig. 10(a). Figure 10(b) was taken at one cycle before the fracture. A small delamination of a surface layer at free edge was observed as circled with a red in Fig. 10(b). The specimen was abruptly broken during the 638th loading as shown in Fig. 10(c). All of the unimpacted specimens were catastrophically fractured as shown in Fig. 10.

(a) N=636 (b) N=637 (c) N=638

Fig. 10. Photographs of an unimpacted specimen in fatigue.
(Fatigue life of this specimen was 638.)

Figure 11 shows photographs of an impacted specimen in fatigue. This specimen had been induced the largest level delamination (D_e/b of 0.37) by the impact loading which is almost comparable to the specimen in Fig. 9. The specimen was cyclically subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 345 MPa. The number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 47. Figures 11(a) and (b) represent the impacted side and the rear side of the specimen loaded at the 46th cycle, respectively. The impact crater and its vicinity were sunk into the out-of-plane direction and the thin surface layer on the rear side of the specimen was locally buckled as shown in Figs. 11(a) and (b). Figures 11(c) and (d) were the photographs taken at the beginning of the fatigue life cycle. Figures 11(c) and (d) show the hollow of the impacted side and the local buckling of the rear surface disappeared except for the impact crater and the rear bulge by the delamination, respectively. The specimen was abruptly fractured at the 47th loading as shown in Figs. 11(e) and (f).

Figure 12 shows photographs in the fatigue test of a specimen with a comparatively small impact-induced delamination (D_e/b of 0.19). The specimen was cyclically subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 380 MPa. The number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 1,992. Figures 12(a) and (b) represent the impacted side and the rear side of the specimen loaded at the 1,836th cycle, respectively. In the case of the specimens with small impact damage, the impact crater and its vicinity did not deform to the out-of-plane direction, which was quite dissimilar from the specimens with a large delamination as in Figs. 11 (a) and (b). Cracks emanated from the edge of the impact crater in the width direction as shown in Fig. 12(a). At the end of the fatigue life, the cracks at the impacted surface grew transversely and the specimen bowed at the center of the gage area as shown in Figs. 12 (c) and (d). The specimen was abruptly fractured at the 1,992nd loading as shown in Figs. 12(e) and (f).

A post-impact fatigue test was interrupted in order to inspect an interior damage just after the specimen made an abrupt rupture sound. The specimen with middle-sized impact damage (D_e/b of 0.24) was subjected to the 563rd loading with a maximum compressive stress of 354 MPa. The specimen was sectioned in the vicinity of the impact crater using a diamond-impregnated saw, and the cross sections were examined with a scanning electron microscope. Abrasive papers were used to polish the cross-section so that interior regions of the laminate could be inspected. Figure 13(a) shows an ultrasonic C-scan image of the specimen before the fatigue test and a portion examined microscopically. Figure 13(b) indicates an interlaminar delamination between the 0-degree layer and the -45-degree layer near the rear surface. Figure 13(c) shows a magnified view of a purple rectangle in Fig. 13(b) and reveals fiber microbuckling and kinking occurred in the 0-degree layer at the delamination edge.

The observed damage patterns such as the local buckling, the delamination growth, the lateral cracks, the microbuckling and the kinking, as in Figs. 9 and 11-13, are quite similar to those in open-hole laminates and impacted laminates under uniaxial compression [4,10]. In the post-impact compression fatigue, these local damages may be accumulated and mechanical properties of the laminate are gradually degraded as shown in Fig. 8. The fatigue behavior of damage accumulation may lead to the gentler gradient of the S-N curves as shown in Fig. 7.

(a) Impacted side at N=46

(b) Rear side at N=46

(c) Impacted side at the beginning of N=47

(d) Rear side at the beginning of N=47

(e) Impacted side at N=47

(f) Rear side at N=47

Fig. 11. Photographs of an impacted specimen with a ratio D_e/b of 0.37 in fatigue. (Fatigue life of this specimen was 47.)

(a) Impacted side at N=1,836

(b) Rear side at N=1,836

(c) Impacted side at N=1,991

(d) Rear side at N=1,991

(e) Impacted side at N=1,992

(f) Rear side at N=1,992

Fig. 12. Photographs of an impacted specimen with a ratio D_e/b of 0.19 in fatigue.
(Fatigue life of this specimen was 1,992.)

CONCLUSIONS

1. The impact-induced damage reduced the compression fatigue performance of the laminate and the S-N curves for the impacted specimens had a gentler gradient than that for the unimpacted specimens.
2. The damage patterns observed in the post-impact compression fatigue tests were quite similar to those in open-hole laminates and impacted laminates under uniaxial compression.
3. Amounts of impact damage affected compression fatigue behavior. In the case of the specimens with large impact damage, the rear side delamination grew widthwise during compression fatigue.

On the other hand, in the case of the specimens with small impact damage, lateral cracks emanated from the edge of the impact crater during fatigue.

4. Fiber microbuckling and kinking were observed in the 0-degree layer of the specimen under post-impact compression fatigue.

(a) Ultrasonic C-scan image and cut line (b) Scanning electron micrograph (c) Magnified view of (b)

Fig. 13. Scanning electron photographs showing fiber microbuckling and kinking in a laminate.

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